

Electrode kinetics and polarographic study of mixed ligand complexes of zinc(II)-L-aminoacidate- α -picoline system

Seema Vajhallya and Farid Khan*

Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar-470 003, India

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Polarographic technique has been used to determine the stability constants ($\log \beta$) of ternary complexes of Zn^{II} with L-lysine, L-ornithine, L-serine, L-phenylglycine, L-phenylalanine, L-glutamic acid and L-aspartic acid as primary ligands and α -picoline as secondary ligand at $pH = 8.50 \pm 0.01$ and ionic strength $\mu = 1.0 M$ ($NaClO_4$) at 25° . The waves of Zn and its complexes are quasireversible. Zn forms 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 complexes. The kinetic parameters are also determined.

Amino acids are well known chelating agents and play an important role in biology, pharmacy, and laboratory reagents¹. The amino acid compounds are biologically active creating considerable interest in their metal complexes². The kinetic parameters are very useful to study the nature of electrode process. Therefore, the study of their complexes has great significance specially when they form complexes with L-amino acids. A survey of literature reveals no reference regarding the ternary complexes of Zn with L-lysine, L-ornithine, L-threonine, L-serine, L-phenylglycine, L-phenylalanine, L-glutamic acid, L-aspartic acid as primary ligands and α -picoline as secondary ligand followed by the kinetic parameters of the corresponding electrode reactions, hence the present study was undertaken.

Results and Discussion

Zn^{II} gave a well defined two-electron quasireversible reduction wave in $1.0 M NaClO_4$ at $pH 8.50 \pm 0.01$ at 25° . The value of $E_{1/2}$ quasireversible of Zn^{II} was $-1.010 V$ vs SCE which by Gellings method³ gave $(E_{1/2})_{rev} = -0.989 V$. In all the cases, the irreversibility increased with increase in concentration of ligands.

L-Amino acid- α -picoline ternary complexes : This system was studied at $pH 8.50 \pm 0.01$ and at 25° . The free ligand concentrations of L-amino acids were calculated by their pK_2^H and experimental pH of the system. Ternary complexes were investigated at two fixed concentrations of α -picoline (viz. 0.025 and 0.050 M) and varying the concentration of L-amino acidate (0.5 to 50 mM). The waves for Zn^{II} and its complexes were quasireversible as confirmed by the kinetic parameters of Zn and its complexes as given in Table 1.

The overall stability constant of mixed ligand complex species were evaluated by employing Schaap and McMaster method⁴ which confirmed the formation of 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 complexes. All the values of stability constant of (Zn-L-aminoacidate- α -picoline) system are presented in Table 2. The data and plots of $F_{ij}[X,Y]$ vs [X]

(where X = concentration of L-lysine and Y = concentration of α -picoline) are given in Table 3 and Fig. 1 respec-

Fig. 1. Plots of Zn-L-lysinate- α -picoline system : (\diamond) $F_{00}[X,Y] \times 10^{-1}$, (\blacklozenge) $F_{10}[X,Y] \times 10^{-4}$, (+) $F_{20}[X,Y] \times 10^{-6}$ (H) $F_{30}[X,Y] \times 10^{-7}$.

tively. The plots^{3,5} of $[E-(0.0591/n) \log (i_d-i)/i]$ vs i for Zn and its complexes are given in Fig. 2. A plots⁶ of $\log (Z-1)$ vs $(E_{1/2}-E)$ for Zn and its complexes were made.

Fig. 2. Plots of $[E-(RT/nF) \log ((i_d-i)/i)]$ vs i of Zn-L-lysinate- α -picoline system : (■) 0.5, (◇) 1, (▲) 2, (□) 3, (◇) 4, (Δ) 5, (●) 6, (★) 8, (▼) 10, (◊) 20, (★) 30, (V) 40 and (V) 50 mM.

The stability of mixed ligand complexes can be compared with binary complexes⁷ by using the equation,

$$\log K_m = \log \beta_{11} - 1/2[\log \beta_{20} + \log \beta_{02}]$$

The values of $\log K_m$ are 0.530, -0.425, 0.805, -0.703, -0.687, -0.585 and 0.141 respectively, for [Zn-L-lys.- α -pic], [Zn-L-orn.- α -pic.], [Zn-L-threo.- α -pic.], [Zn-L-ser.- α -pic.], [Zn-L-phenylgly.- α -pic.], [Zn-L-phenylala.- α -pic.], [Zn-L-asp.- α -pic.] systems. The positive values of $\log K_m$ indicate that the ternary complexes are more stable than the binary complexes, while the negative values indicate that the binary complexes are more stable than the ternary complexes⁴.

The values of standard rate constant (K) of Zn and its complexes are of the order of $10^{-3} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$, confirming that the electrode process are quasireversible⁸. The charge transfer coefficient α -which can be regarded as the fraction of the applied potential, which either assists or hinders the process under consideration is also having the values as expected⁹. It is clear from the values of standard rate constant that the reduction of electroactive species at the surface of dropping mercury electrode is not fast.

The sequence of stability constants is L-lysine < L-ornithine < L-threonine < L-serine < L-phenylglycine < L-phenylalanine < L-glutamic acid < L-aspartic acid. It has been observed that as the size of amino acid is increased, the stability of complexes decreases¹⁰. The stability of L-lysinate complex is minimum owing to its lowest pK value compared to rest of the L-amino acids. As the pK value decreases, the stability of complex decreases¹⁰. In case of L-serine and L-threonine, the stability of the latter is less than the L-serine complex owing to the fact that electron-withdrawing OH⁻ group is nearer to L-threoninate complex than L-serinate complex, causing greater repulsive forces between metal and OH⁻ group in L-threonine complexes than L-serine complexes.

As mentioned earlier, as the size of amino acids increases, the stability of complexes decreases¹⁰. This effect of size on stability is observed in all the selected amino

Table I. Kinetic parameters of Zn^{II}-L-lysinate- α -picoline system

L-Lys $\times 10^{-3} M$	[Zn ^{II}] = 0.5 mM, $\mu = 1.0 M$ NaClO ₄ , pH = 8.50 \pm 0.01, Temp = 25 ^o [α -Picoline] = 0.025 M (Fixed)						[α -Picoline] = 0.050 M (Fixed)					
	(E _{1/2}) _{QR} -V vs SCE	Slope mV	α	λ	D _{1/2} $\times 10^3$ cm ² s ⁻¹	K $\times 10^3$ cm s ⁻¹	(E _{1/2}) _{QR} -V vs SCE	Slope mV	α	λ	D _{1/2} $\times 10^3$ cm ² s ⁻¹	K $\times 10^3$ cm s ⁻¹
0.00	1.010						1.010					
0.50	1.055	40.0	0.487	1.32	4.32	5.72	1.062	37.5	0.478	1.32	4.32	5.72
1.00	1.075	40.0	0.529	1.32	4.32	5.72	1.077	40.0	0.490	1.05	4.25	4.47
2.00	1.085	37.5	0.457	1.18	4.25	5.02	1.094	37.5	0.487	1.05	4.25	4.47
3.00	1.090	40.0	0.454	1.18	4.25	5.02	1.107	37.5	0.470	1.18	4.18	4.49
4.00	1.105	35.0	0.504	1.05	4.25	4.47	1.114	40.0	0.462	1.25	4.11	5.14
5.00	1.110	35.0	0.519	1.32	4.18	5.54	1.119	40.0	0.490	1.05	4.11	4.33
6.00	1.125	37.5	0.438	1.18	4.11	4.86	1.129	42.5	0.438	1.18	4.11	4.86
8.00	1.126	37.5	0.408	1.16	4.11	4.80	1.134	37.5	0.478	1.18	4.04	4.77
10.00	1.127	35.0	0.457	1.48	4.11	6.11	1.136	37.5	0.408	1.48	4.04	6.01
20.00	1.153	40.0	0.487	1.25	3.98	4.97	1.155	40.0	0.494	1.18	3.98	4.69
30.00	1.165	40.0	0.460	1.18	3.98	4.69	1.165	37.5	0.478	1.32	3.91	5.18
40.00	1.175	40.0	0.519	0.99	3.91	3.88	1.176	42.5	0.487	1.32	3.84	5.08
50.00	1.180	40.0	0.460	1.25	3.84	4.80	1.182	37.5	0.487	1.18	3.77	4.45

Table 2. Stability constants of Zn^{II}-L-aminoacidate- α -picoline system

[Zn^{II}] = 0.5 mM, μ = 1.0M NaClO₄, pH = 8.50 \pm 0.01, Temp. = 25^o

Ligands	pK ₂ ^H	Binary complexes ^a							
		log β_{01}	log β_{02}	log β_{10}	log β_{20}	log β_{30}	log β_{11}	log β_{12}	log β_{21}
L-Lysine	8.95	—	—	3.85	6.75	9.30	4.32	7.00	9.50
L-Ornithine	8.98	—	—	3.92	6.86	9.49	4.48	7.25	9.74
L-Threonine	9.00	—	—	4.34	7.46	9.62	4.49	7.60	9.90
L-Serine	9.20	—	—	4.41	7.59	9.80	4.57	7.85	—
L-Phenylglycine	9.23	—	—	4.48	7.73	9.89	4.65	—	10.18
L-Phenylalanine	9.30	—	—	4.55	7.86	10.08	4.82	—	10.42
L-Glutamic acid	9.67	—	—	5.60	8.90	10.10	—	9.13	10.53
L-Aspartic acid	9.82	—	—	5.67	9.02	10.30	6.13	9.38	10.77
α -Picoline ^b	—	1.65	2.95	—	—	—	—	—	—

^aRef. 7. ^bRef. 12.

Table 3. Polarographic characteristics and $F_{ij}[X, Y]$ values for the Zn^{II}-L-lysinate- α -picoline system

[Zn^{II}] = 0.5 mM, μ = 1.0 M NaClO₄, pH = 8.50 \pm 0.01, Temp. = 25^o

[α -Picoline] = 0.025M (Fixed)										[α -Picoline] = 0.050 M (Fixed)						
L-Lys. $\times 10^3$ M	$(E_{1/2})_{0R}$ -V	$(E_{1/2})_c$ -V	$\Delta E_{1/2}$ V	$\log \frac{I_m}{I_c}$	$F_{00}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^{-1}$	$F_{10}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^{-1}$	$F_{20}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^{-7}$	$F_{30}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^{-9}$	$(E_{1/2})_{0R}$ -V	$(E_{1/2})_c$ -V	$\Delta E_{1/2}$ V	$\log \frac{I_m}{I_c}$	$F_{00}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^{-1}$	$F_{10}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^{-1}$	$F_{20}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^{-7}$	$F_{30}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^{-9}$
0.00	1.010	0.989							1.010	0.989						
0.50	1.055	1.032	0.043	0.0068	3.10	5.66	8.56	1.99	1.062	1.042	0.053	0.0068	6.32	11.54	16.47	1.99
1.00	1.075	1.048	0.059	0.0068	10.31	10.04	8.66	1.99	1.077	1.054	0.065	0.0137	17.11	19.17	16.57	1.97
2.00	1.085	1.064	0.075	0.0137	38.44	19.10	8.86	1.99	1.094	1.073	0.084	0.0137	74.24	16.57	16.76	1.98
3.00	1.090	1.075	0.086	0.0137	85.97	28.56	9.06	1.97	1.107	1.083	0.094	0.0208	163.21	36.85	16.97	1.99
4.00	1.105	1.082	0.093	0.0137	153.97	38.42	9.26	1.98	1.114	1.090	0.101	0.0280	288.51	71.99	17.16	1.99
5.00	1.110	1.088	0.099	0.0208	243.70	48.68	9.46	1.99	1.119	1.096	0.107	0.0280	451.32	90.15	17.36	1.99
6.00	1.125	1.093	0.104	0.0280	356.35	59.34	9.65	1.99	1.129	1.100	0.111	0.0280	640.85	106.71	17.56	1.99
8.00	1.126	1.100	0.111	0.0280	655.21	81.86	10.06	1.99	1.134	1.108	0.119	0.0353	1176.85	147.03	17.96	1.99
10.00	1.127	1.107	0.118	0.0280	1059.14	105.88	10.45	1.99	1.136	1.114	0.125	0.0353	1870.04	186.94	18.36	1.99
20.00	1.153	1.126	0.137	0.0353	5004.04	250.18	12.44	1.99	1.155	1.132	0.143	0.0427	8208.27	410.38	20.35	1.99
30.00	1.165	1.138	0.149	0.0427	1302.80	434.28	14.43	1.99	1.165	1.144	0.155	0.0503	20209.24	673.62	22.34	1.99
40.00	1.175	1.147	0.158	0.0503	20327.78	658.18	16.42	1.99	1.176	1.152	0.163	0.0579	39066.96	976.66	24.33	1.99
50.00	1.180	1.154	0.165	0.0579	46094.66	921.88	18.41	1.99	1.182	1.159	0.170	0.0658	65975.41	131.49	26.32	1.99
			log A = 0.424			log C = 7.92					log A = 0.73		log C = 8.21			
			log B = 4.14			log D = 9.30					log B = 4.52		log D = 9.30			

acids except in the case of L-phenylglycine and L-phenylalanine where the order is reserved, i.e. L-phenylglycine < L-phenylalanine. This could be attributed to the presence of phenyl group at α -carbon atom in L-phenylglycine, whereas it is at β -carbon atom in case of L-phenylalanine causing greater repulsive forces in the former than in the latter.

The higher stability of L-aspartate complexes than L-glutamate complex is obvious from the chelate ring formation in these amino acids; the aspartate forms one five- and one six-membered ring with the metal while L-glutamate forming one six- and one seven-membered ring⁷. As the size of ring increases the stability of complex decreases⁷. The stabilities of L-glutamate and L-aspartate complexes, are greater than those of the L-lysinate, L-ornithinate, L-serinate, L-phenylglycinate and L-phenylalaninate complexes due to large difference in their basic strength.

Experimental

L-Amino acids (Lobachem) and α -picoline (Fluka)

solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. The purity of L-amino acids was checked by chromatographic method¹¹. The concentrations of metal ions and NaClO₄ in the test solution were 0.5 mM and 1.0 M respectively. The pH of the test solution was adjusted to 8.50 \pm 0.01 by adding requisite amount of sodium hydroxide and perchloric acid solutions. The test solutions were deaerated by passing pure hydrogen before recording C-V data.

The current-voltage curves were measured on a manual polarograph using Toshniwal PL-50 polyflex galvanometer. The dropping mercury electrode had capillary characteristics (vs SCE) $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.40 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ at effective mercury height of 60.02 cm. An Elico LI-120 pH meter fitted with glass and saturated calomel electrodes was used. All the measurements were made at 25^o.

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